

LECTURERS' METHODS IN TEACHING SPEAKING

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Abstract: The article discusses modern methods of preparing and conducting lectures and seminars on foreign language teaching methods, revealing the potential of teachers and students, as well as new approaches to teaching speaking skills.

Keywords: modern educational technologies, information technologies, jigsaw, acting from a script, prepared talks, student-team learning, debate, discussion.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются современные методы подготовки и проведения лекций и семинаров по методам обучения иностранному языку, раскрывающие потенциал преподавателей и студентов, а также новые подходы к обучению разговорной речи.

Ключевые слова: современные образовательные технологии, информационные технологии, головоломка, игра по сценарию, предварительные выступления, групповое обучение, дебаты, дискуссия.

Introduction

Speaking English lessons, in particular, are successful and effective when the lecturers are competent and using the right teaching techniques. Despite the significance of such elements in effective instruction, the results are far from ideal. Surprisingly, a lot of students deal with these issues in the classroom. The most frequent causes of this issue are the learners' limited vocabulary, lack of enthusiasm, and lack of practice in speaking the target language.

A modern student does not perceive classical lectures, traditionally organized types of practical and independent work, since he relies on the use of modern educational technologies. Usually a lecture is a transfer of ready-made knowledge through a monologue form of communication. With the development of information technologies in the educational process, electronic lectures were also conducted, characterized by a block diagram of the construction of the material, a developed hypertext structure, the use of demonstration material, which helps to increase the efficiency of students' assimilation of educational information. The advantages of using information technologies can be traced in the process of teaching the following disciplines: theory and methods of teaching foreign languages, modern pedagogical technologies, modern means of evaluating learning outcomes, etc.

Therefore, English lecturers must employ a variety of pertinent teaching tactics in order to assist students in learning English and enhance their speaking talents in terms of accuracy and fluency. In order to aid students in the process of learning the target language, lecturers must also present classroom activities that encourage the usage of English as much as possible both within and outside of the classroom. Language is learned by practice, according to M. F. Patel and P. M. Jain, and students will get better the more they are exposed to the target language. According to T. Hedge, who supports this notion, when language learners process the available linguistic input, they will require.

One illustration of these beneficial activities is encouraging pupils to converse socially in English in the classroom. It is crucial to consider both "the contexts in which individuals learn" and the characteristics of the particular learner, according to B. Norton and K. Toohey. A good lecturer also knows why they do what they do. In other words, they are knowledgeable about the subject matter they are teaching while also having a broad understanding of the many and numerous different teaching tactics, methods, and strategies.

There is no doubt that different lecturers will organize classroom activities differently and use different methods in the language classroom due to differences in competency, experience, knowledge, and personalities. However, it is thought that a knowledgeable and skilled lecturer will be able to make better choices during the teaching process. As a result, the researcher made the decision to actively watch and investigate the teaching strategies employed by the lecturers in the speaking class as well as how those strategies are executed in the classroom.

There are a number of activities that can be used to teach speaking, including the following:

1. Jigsaw; the teacher organizes the work at the seminars on the technology "Saw" (Jigsaw), which involves group work of students of different levels of performance. The audience is divided into groups of five people, they are asked five questions on the topic of the seminar. Each member of the group chooses one question and becomes the "expert" on that question in their group. At a practical lesson, students are given 20 minutes to discuss the issue in an expert group, where they discuss, ask, complement each other. For the next 20-25 minutes, the "experts", returning to their original groups, take turns telling all the information they have collected on their question.

As a result of joint work, each student should get a general idea of what the other members of his group have prepared. The remaining time of the seminar is devoted to a joint discussion of all questions, the teacher can ask any student to answer any of the five questions. The final score of the group is the sum of the points received for the answer of each of the members of the group. This technology seems to be effective in increasing the motivation for independent work. At seminars organized according to the "Jigsaw" method, students have to process a large amount of various modern methodological and scientific literature in order to be truly an expert in their field.

The advantage of this method is that each student is brought up with individual responsibility for the success of the whole team, although in practice there were difficulties in this regard. The observations made by the teacher showed that the students were reluctant to start work in groups, since it was important for everyone to get a grade for their answer. The bias of assessment, associated with the fact that each member of the group receives an overall assessment of the group, regardless of the degree of preparedness.

Student Team Learning; the main idea of which is to create conditions for active joint learning activities of students in different learning situations. Students are grouped into groups, each of which is offered a separate task. The whole group is interested in the assimilation of educational information by each of its members, since the success of the team depends on this. This encourages team members to follow each other's progress and the whole team to come to the aid of their comrade in mastering the material.

The peculiarity of learning in a team is that each student earns points by improving his own previous results, and not by comparing with the results of other group members. This gives advanced, intermediate and backward students an equal opportunity to earn points for their team. At the same time, the teacher differentiates the complexity of tasks for strong and weak students.

2. Acting from a script; students act out dialogue they have created for themselves, scenes from plays, or the script from their textbook.

3. Classroom discussion; this can take the shape of a formal, multi-staged discussion or an informal, small-group exchange.

4. Debate; Students prepare arguments for and against numerous propositions in a debate, after which they offer their points of view on a certain issue.

5. Prepared Talks; one or more students give a presentation on a subject of their own choosing. The pupils will have some time to get ready for their speech. According to [11], there are a number of qualities that encourage the effective teaching of speaking, including the following. 1) Students should have plenty of opportunities to speak during class communication time; 2) participation in class discussion should not be dominated by a small number of talkative students; rather, all students should have an equal opportunity to speak, and contributions should be distributed fairly; 3) picking an engaging and novel subject for study should encourage students to help with meeting learning objectives.

6. Tables and diagrams into electronic format (presentation in Power Point) are now used by teachers in lectures that require students to be able to operate with abstract categories. The diagrams and tables clearly reflect the relationship between key concepts and basic definitions, which makes it as easy as possible to assimilate the studied material. A computer, a screen and a multimedia projector are used to demonstrate materials. After the lecture course in theoretical disciplines, seminars are organized to consolidate the knowledge gained by students during listening to lectures

and independent work on the subject. Seminars usually take the form of a detailed conversation, discussion of reports and abstracts, a debate seminar, commented reading, exercises for independent thinking, written (test) work, etc.

The choice of the form of conducting a seminar on the theory and methodology of teaching foreign languages, of course, depends on the content of the topic and the nature of the sources and manuals recommended for it, on the level of preparedness, organization and efficiency of students.

Conclusion

As we can see, the use of modern technologies in lectures and seminars has a number of positive aspects: the attitude of students to theoretical subjects is clearly changing, the constant interest in learning them is increasing, the level of knowledge is the understanding of the educational material. deepens. Thus, if the lecturer, who always gives lectures, uses different techniques in the lectures, the level of students' mastery will also increase. It is possible to improve the quality of the lesson through a creative approach.

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